

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

AMELIORATIVE STATUS AND FERTILITY PRESERVATION OF SOILS IN THE KURA-ARAS LOWLAND

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Abstract

Preservation of soil fertility remains one of the key factors in ensuring food security. In recent years, the completion of agrarian reforms in Azerbaijan has fostered the emergence of new production relationships, facilitating increased agricultural productivity. However, ongoing global climate change processes, also observed in Azerbaijan, have caused alterations in soil cover, negatively impacting the productivity and sustainability of irrigated agricultural lands. The Kura-Aras Lowland, which represents Azerbaijan's principal crop production zone, possesses favorable edaphic conditions for agricultural activities. The ameliorative condition and fertility conservation of these soils remain among the primary concerns for soil scientists. Based on studies conducted on irrigated soils under cotton and cereal cultivation in the Salyan plain and Southern Mughan, it was established that the soils exhibit clayey to silty clay texture, with physical clay content ranging from 60.38% to 65.71%. The electrical conductivity values, expressed as total soluble salts (dry residue), ranged from 0.11% to 0.23%, classifying the soils as non-saline to slightly saline.

Keywords: collector-drainage system, soil salinization, soil fertility, irrigation-induced erosion, anthropogenic impact, salt composition.

Introduction

Soil resources constitute the fundamental basis for agricultural production. However, unsustainable land management practices - including improper tillage and excessive agrochemical application - have led to significant soil contamination and degradation processes [4, p.17-19]. Presently, both natural and anthropogenic factors result in the degradation of vast areas of productive land globally. Climate change has emerged as a major global challenge, posing direct threats to agriculture, water resources, and coastal ecosystems [13]. In Azerbaijan, ongoing climatic warming accelerates organic matter mineralization, leading to rapid depletion of soil organic carbon (humus), thereby compromising soil fertility. These impacts are increasingly recognized as a global environmental concern. Prolonged drought periods have driven the expansion of irrigation zones; however, climate change simultaneously intensifies soil erosion processes, leading to deterioration of topsoil horizons and substantial yield reductions.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on irrigated croplands located in the Seyidsadygly sector of the Salyan plain and the Aghayri village of Bilasuvar District in Southern Mughan, each covering 3 ha. Composite soil samples were collected from georeferenced sampling sites. Standard laboratory analyses were carried out in ac-

cordance with widely adopted soil science methodologies, including determination of granulometric composition, exchangeable bases, pH, soluble salt content, and humus content [1, p.410-416].

Results and Discussion

Soil productivity is determined by the synergistic interaction of agrotechnical, agrochemical, and ameliorative measures, alongside inherent fertility characteristics. The theoretical foundations of soil fertility are strongly associated with V.R. Williams, who analyzed fertility formation in relation to soil genesis and developed principles for its enhancement. Fertility is manifested through crop yields, phytomass production, nutrient availability, humus content and favorable ecological attributes [9, p.42-44]. Following Azerbaijan's independence, significant reforms in land management have been undertaken since 1993, contributing to the preservation and restoration of soil fertility on arable lands. However, under intensifying anthropogenic pressures, protection and regeneration of these valuable resources remain critical challenges.

Improper land management not only depresses crop yields but also destabilizes ecological balance and triggers irreversible soil degradation processes. Stabilizing and improving soil fertility not only ensures food security but also promotes socioeconomic development and safeguards environmental integrity for future generations. Conversely, unsustainable land use leads to

depletion of beneficial soil properties, rendering land agriculturally unproductive. Therefore, safeguarding soil fertility and optimizing land utilization are of paramount importance for sustainable development in the agro-sector [8, p.19-43].

Rapid population growth, urban sprawl, and expanding settlements have significantly intensified anthropogenic pressures on soil resources. Despite existing collector-drainage networks, over 600,000 ha of irrigated land in Azerbaijan is currently affected by salinization. Salt accumulation severely suppresses soil productivity, in many cases rendering crop cultivation unfeasible. Salinization alters soil structure, impairs water and nutrient regimes, disrupts photosynthetic activity, and leads to land withdrawal from agricultural production [13].

Approximately 97% of Azerbaijan's irrigated agricultural lands, and over 90% of saline soils, are concentrated in the Kura-Aras Lowland [2, p.4-7]. According to M.P. Babayev's extensive surveys, 51.78% (4.4 million ha) of Azerbaijan's land is arable, of which 40% is under cultivation. The dominant soil types include gray soils (*Calcic Kastanozems*), meadow-gray soils (*LuvicGleysols*), and brown soils (*Cambisols*), with variable granulometric composition ranging from sandy to clayey textures. Periodic disruptions in irrigation networks have resulted in the formation of paleopedogenic and anthropogenically modified horizons within the soil profile. Irrigation-induced erosion depletes topsoil fertility, degrades hydro-physical properties, and destabilizes the agro-ecosystem.

Soils in the Kura-Aras Lowland exhibit high carbonate accumulation, primarily due to parent material composition and calcium-carbonate-rich irrigation water. Field observations revealed that irrigation on sloping lands contributed to fertility depletion and subsequent exclusion of degraded lands from agricultural use [3, p.7-12]. Major degradation processes include erosion, primary and secondary salinization, solonetz

formation, compaction, technogenic disturbance, humus depletion, and deterioration of hydrochemical properties. Salinization not only reduces crop yields but also accelerates desertification, contributes to loss of biodiversity, and triggers profound alterations in natural landscapes. It disrupts soil aeration, thermal and nutritional regimes, weakens biochemical cycling, and suppresses photosynthesis. Severely saline soils often become barren and agriculturally unusable [10, p.8-15].

V.R.Volobuyev comprehensively described the geomorphological characteristics of the Kura-Aras Lowland, highlighting the role of Caspian Sea transgressions and regressions in shaping the landscape. The region exhibits a semi-arid steppe to semi-desert climate. Its floristic composition has been extensively studied by A.A.Grossheim, L.I.Prilipko, I.N.Beydeman, A.S.Preobrazhensky, and others. In recent decades, anthropogenic pressure has further intensified soil salinization across the lowland. The Salyan Plain, extensively used for intensive cropping, exhibits varying degrees of salinization. Numerous scholars, including A.K.Behbudov, Kh.F.Jafarov, N.A.Dimo, V.R.Volobuyev, M.E.Salayev, H.A.Aliyev, M.P.Babayev, Q.Sh.Mammadov, and M.Q.Mustafayev, have conducted detailed investigations in this region. The Salyan plain encompasses approximately 149,000 ha, of which 46,000 ha are cultivated. Groundwater depths fluctuate between 5 to 10.5 meters, depending on seasonal and topographic variations. The prevalent soils include meadow-gray, gray-meadow, meadow-swamp, and associated soil types. The natural vegetation of the Salyan plain was extensively documented by A.Q.Grossheim in 1929 [5, p.13].

Soil sampling from the experimental plots revealed that soluble salt concentrations peaked below the 0-25 cm horizon, ranging between 0.11% and 0.20%, classifying these soils as non-saline to slightly saline (Figures 1). Soil pH values ranged between 7.6 and 7.7 [7, p.66-69].

Figures 1. Diagram of salt changes in the study area (cotton and grain lands, Salyan plain)

The sum of exchangeable bases ranged from 24.17–27.87 meq/100g in the 0–50 cm horizon and 27.02–33.87 meq/100g in the 0–100 cm horizon.

Parallel studies in Aghayri village (Bilasuvan District, Southern Mughan) showed that the geomorphology was shaped by Caspian Sea oscillations and fluvial

deposition from the Araz and Bolgar rivers [11, p.40; 12, p.104-124]. Soils are primarily classified as meadow-gray (*Calcic Kastanozems*). Soluble salt contents ranged from 0.11% to 0.23%, with salinity type predominantly chloride-sulfate (Figure 2, 3). [6, p.64-68]

Figure 2. Variations in soluble salt content under wheat cropping systems (Southern Mughan)

Figure 3. Variations in soluble salt content under cotton cropping systems (Southern Mughan).

The sum of exchangeable bases in the surface 0–25 cm layer ranged from 28.40 to 36.90 meq/100g, while in deeper horizons it ranged from 30.25 to 49.70 meq/100g. Soil pH varied between 7.68 and 7.93.

Conclusion

1. Both experimental areas were characterized as non-saline to moderately saline, making them suitable for the cultivation of diverse agricultural crops.

2. In Salyan Plain, salt concentrations ranged from 0.11% to 0.20%; in Southern Mughan, from 0.11% to 0.23%. The dominant salinity type was identified a schloride-sulfate.

3. Strict adherence to appropriate irrigation regimes is essential for maintaining soil fertility.

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